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**The Platform for Sharing, Initiating and
Learning Citizen Science in Europe**

Deliverable D7.2

Interim Impact Assessment Report

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Abstract	This deliverable is based on Task 7.2 & 7.3, and presents the interim impact assessment report. It discusses the evaluation activities of the project until year 2 and illustrates an analysis of the corresponding results. It also includes an assessment of the EU-Citizen.Science platform, the impact on involved institutions and countries as well as an overall progress report. The evaluation matrix provides an overview of KPIs collected from the different work packages and a summary of main lessons learned concerning the immediate and short term outcomes of the project.
Keywords	EU-Citizen.Science, Citizen Science, Evaluation, Impact Assessment

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3.0	2.12.	Teresa Schaefer (ZSI), Barbara Kieslinger (ZSI)	Content for Executive Summary, Introduction, Conclusions; Finalisation of chapters 3-6
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Definitions and Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
CS	Citizen Science
EC	European Commission

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ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
H2020	Horizon 2020
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LFA	Logic Framework Approach
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SUS	System Usability Questionnaire
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

The deliverable, D7.2. Interim Impact Assessment Report, presents the results from a range of evaluation activities conducted in the second year of the project. The main focus of activities was still formative, especially when it comes to the portal. The main aim at this phase of the project is to collect feedback to further improve and optimise the portal as the central place for sharing, learning and initiating Citizen Science in Europe. Evaluation activities comprised three main areas: 1) assessing the progress of the project, also compared to the objectives set in the initial work plan and related to a set of defined performance indicators; 2) investigating acceptance factors of the newly developed platform and looking into the details of the current platform usage, not only indicating how far we reached out to the European Citizen Science community but also learning about the communities' interests; and 3) capturing the organisational impact of the project on the partner institutions involved, as well as understanding the project's impact on the broader mainstreaming of Citizen Science in different European regions and countries. The main finding from all these activities is that the project succeeded in establishing a strong basis that can be used in the final project year to create a vivid and connected Citizen Science community in Europe.

In 2020 two versions of the EU-Citizen.Science platform were released and evaluated. Structured feedback from users was shared with the technical development team and the community manager to make ongoing iterative improvements. Thus, we have created a stable version of a platform that attracted more users (20,000 and 112,000 page views) than we would have planned for in the first month of runtime. The portal is known in the European Citizen Science community, especially amongst researchers and experts in Citizen Science. We created a well-defined process on how to select and upload resources to this platform. This process has already been applied to upload the current set of nearly 90 resources that can be found on the portal. The elaboration of the ECSA Characteristics of Citizen Science¹ is another important outcome of the project, which was not part of the original work plan but was undertaken in response to the needs of the community to better understand what is and is not Citizen Science.

Other important documents produced by the consortium include the training need analysis², which is the basis for the training modules that will be developed over the coming months, and the resource gap analysis³, which will guide further activities on the selection and elaboration of resources uploaded to the platform. In this work, the partners had to address several challenges, related to the diverse expectations from the large range of stakeholders involved in Citizen Science, the diverse understandings about what "quality" means related to shared resources on the platform, a broad range of opinions on what Citizen Science is and what not, and of course the COVID-19 situation that influenced the work in all work packages, but specifically the planned dissemination and outreach activities. The large number of experts on Citizen Science involved in this consortium helped to address these challenges and flexibly react to newly arising needs. Examples are for instance the

¹ The ECSA Characteristics of Citizen Science, <https://zenodo.org/communities/citscicharacteristics>

² Deliverable 5.2. Design of training activities and materials, <https://zenodo.org/record/4010558>

³ Deliverable 3.2 Citizen Science resource gap and opportunities analysis, <https://zenodo.org/record/4004177>

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organisation of a series of webinars that replaced planned face-to-face activities, or the selection and promotion of Citizen Science projects that are doable from home, which was highly accessed during the first Covid-19 lockdown on our portal. Also our dissemination indicators show that we have successfully reached out to the Citizen Science community.

Although we can be satisfied with the first outcomes and state that the project is on track, we know that there is still a lot of work needed to build a vivid community around the portal. A community that not only shares projects or promotes their own organisation on the platform, but also feels responsible for the quality of information shared on the portal, through rating and commenting on resources, as well as actively contributing to a growing number of guidelines, handbooks, articles, tools shared with the community. Also the forum needs to be established as a widely used feature to network and share experiences amongst practitioners, researchers, policy makers etc.

In the upcoming project phase the large number of consortium partners, also those that are involved also to a minor extent, will play an important role. Interviews with them showed that the involvement in EU-Citizen.Science increased the partners' visibility and reputation within their regional and national networks, helped to stress the importance of Citizen Science as a research approach and fostered the work on regional and national infrastructures that support Citizen Science (e.g. national platforms, associations, competence centres etc.). We learned how differently Citizen Science is established and supported in different European countries, with some countries providing strong support infrastructures while others are still relying on personal networks and strong personal involvement to drive and promote this form of collaboration between society and science. Many partners told us that the existence of a stable EU-Citizen.Science portal that offers high quality content will be an important driver of local and national activities in different European member states. Thus we expect a large number of activities around the portal in the coming year and know from reflection exercises with all partners that these activities will involve not only researchers and scientists, but also other stakeholder groups such as schools, policy makers and European citizens more generally. A series of interviews that are organised with all partners at the time of writing this deliverable, as well as another one planned for the end of the project will capture the project impacts on organisational, regional and national levels.

Next to the community building, we see the collaboration with national platform organisations and technical integration of national platforms as an important focus of the final project year. We also think that the specific communication and exchange with stakeholder groups that are not scientists, such as the broader public and policy makers, is a project objective that we will address as a consortium with a large range of expertise and networks.

2 Introduction

The interim impact assessment report discusses the evaluation activities until the end of year 2 and presents an analysis of the corresponding results. The deliverable is structured along the following main chapters:

Chapter 3: *Methodology* shortly introduces the applied evaluation instruments, which are also explained in Detail in D7.1. Evaluation framework.

Chapter 4: the *Progress Assessment* section presents main activities, the challenges encountered, and the outcomes generated by each work package and keeps track of the projects' progress via a number of KPIs that were jointly defined at the start of the project.

Chapter 5: *Evaluation of the EU-Citizen.Science Platform* shows the outcomes from the user acceptance testing of the platform, feedback from the wider ECSA community about the platform use, and detailed analysis of the access statistics.

Chapter 6: *Organisational impact across partners and beyond* shows how far Citizen Science is established in different European member states, how partners are benefiting from the project, and what is expected from EU-Citizen.Science in the years to come.

Chapter 7: *Summary, Conclusions & Outlook*, pulls together the different strings of evaluation, and formulates recommendations on how to further increase the impact of the project.

3 Methodology

Different methods were applied for the interim project evaluation and impact assessment, which are described in more detail in D7.1. Evaluation Framework⁴

For the evaluation of the platform we used three different instruments: we organised two user acceptance tests via walkthroughs to get feedback on usability and usefulness of the developed platform and features; we asked participants of the ECSA conference 2020 for their feedback on the platform via an online questionnaire; and we had a close look at the access statistics of the EU-Citizen.Science portal.

For the overall progress assessment we conducted reflection talks with the work package leaders in separate calls, using the Logic Framework Approach (LFA) introduced in D7.1. to guide our talks. We also collected KPIs from the work packages to compare them with the initially set targets defined in D7.1.

⁴ Deliverable 7.1. Evaluation & Impact Framework, <https://zenodo.org/record/3529269>

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To collect feedback on institutional changes and the project impact on national/eu-wide level we conducted interviews with project partners from 15 countries.

4 Progress assessment

In this progress section we report on the talk with the work package leaders and how the work in the different WPs is progressing overall. Following the original reflection matrix developed in year 1, we give an update on where we stand with the success indicators that have been defined in D7.1 and we reflect on the impact that the global pandemic caused by the COVID-19 virus has had on the project during this year.

4.1. Work package reflections

Based on the Logic Framework Approach (LFA) a reflection matrix was developed and presented in D7.1. It has proven to be a useful instrument to structure and support the dialogue and exchanges between all parties involved, and was used also during the second project year to reflect with the work packages on their progress. The matrix can help to identify problems early on and respond to them accordingly, it can clarify the project's objectives and make them more concrete, specify and adapt the activities, create a joint approach to the project, and make implementation more efficient. In the following we summarise the main points that were addressed in the reflection sessions with each work package.

Work package 2

A main challenge for work package 2 in creating a widely used EU-Citizen.Science Platform has been the integration of all user feedback and aligning it with the content being created in other work packages. A close cooperation with work package 5 for the content and adaptability of the training modules, and an alignment with the quality processes defined in work package 3 has been identified as core for the advancement of the platform.

The main aim of work package 2 is still to establish a community platform that connects existing networks and communities in Citizen Science and is used by a wide number of stakeholders across Europe and beyond. There are good indications that the project is on its way to achieve this aim: a maintenance agreement for the platform has been signed, open source contributions to the platform software are being made, and ECSA feels responsible for taking over the platform after the project has completed the official funding period at the end of 2021. However, additional funding sources might have to be identified in order to maintain the platform and the quality control processes in the future.

Work package 3

Defining the criteria for collecting and sharing tools, guidelines and materials (best practices in Citizen Science) has been difficult, but in the end has been a very rewarding process. Different understandings of what the criteria should address and what they should include were discussed, as well as the overall concept of quality. The challenge was also to create overarching criteria which are detailed enough for the purpose of selecting relevant content to

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be shared on the platform and defining the overall selection process. Detailed descriptions of this process and its challenges can be found in the deliverable of work package 3.

While the defined criteria have received positive feedback and are applied currently, the moderation process for the content is somewhat labour intensive and there needs to be further considerations as to how this can be implemented in the future. Thus, the moderation process is still something to be further reflected in the consortium.

Another critical aspect identified in the work package 3 reflection is the rather low number of rated resources on the platform. The rating function on the platform should be promoted further and it should be made very easy and clear in terms of functionality how a resource can be rated. This will be further explored within work package 2, and the focus on community building over the next year

The expected impact of work package 3 remains that the Citizen Science community will share and use high quality tools, guidelines and materials at European scale, and worldwide. The quality of the tools, guidelines and materials will be supported by positive feedback from different stakeholders in the Citizen Science community.

Work package 4

Work package 4 has been one of the work packages, whose tasks were affected by the pandemic caused by the COVID-19 virus as it defines citizen and policy engagement. While there have been some useful guidelines as how to address these target groups, heightening the guidelines for specific audiences was identified as an important aspect to further work on. Thus, work package 4 will pick certain guidelines that work for specific audiences and add them as a resource on the platform. Responding to the current situation, this includes guidelines on how to engage people in events that are now organised online, and how to respond to the lockdown. Partners in many countries have already started to adjust to the lockdown situation and offer online alternatives. These practices are being shared and packaged into useful guidelines by work package 4.

With regards to policy recommendations, activities are on-going and are represented in the section on awareness raising amongst policy makers of Deliverable 4.2⁵. Based on the valuable feedback that policy makers wish for very structured approaches when being invited to engage with CS initiatives, the audience document for policy makers will include best practices how Citizen Science is used for a positive change for policy makers and the broader public.

With our activities in work package 4, we expect to achieve an increased awareness of Citizen Science amongst the general public and science policy makers across Europe. As an indication for the policy impact we expect Citizen Science methods to be included in an increased number of national science and research policies in Europe.

Work package 5

⁵ Deliverable 4.2: Report on Policy Maker Engagement and Awareness-Raising, <https://zenodo.org/record/3690779>

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The training modules offered by work package 5 are trying to cover identified training needs. These needs are however under continual development and continue to arise. Thus, a certain flexibility throughout the project is requested for this work package. There has been good progress on collecting training resources from a variety of sources and in different languages. The quality criteria defined in work package 3 are very valuable for the selection of the resources to be shared and for assigning metadata.

For the development of specific training modules clear instructions are important, not only for technical aspects, but even more so from a didactical point of view. It is critical to create content fit for online learning, holding someone's interest, being suitable for learning when there is no teacher. Thus, work package 5 has been creating best-practice guidelines on how to do that. The created modules will then also be submitted to internal testing before being launched on the platform.

The expected impact of work package 5 is defined by the availability of high-quality training material for different Citizen Science stakeholders, including those aspects that are currently not covered sufficiently in available training.

Work package 6

Work package 6 was also highly affected by the COVID-19 crisis. As a reaction to COVID-19 and the cancellation of most face-to-face events, the decision was taken to organise a series of webinars, starting with the webinar on the Characteristics of Citizen Science⁶, which was fully booked. Also, as a reaction to COVID-19 the list of Citizen Science activities linked to COVID-19 or doable at home had a lot of reach and mentions. and all projects generally related to COVID-19 were highly disseminated. One strategic move was to use social media promotion to promote CS in general, on specific days with which there was a thematic connection - for example, on the International Day of Peace, a CS project on peace was promoted.

In order to strengthen the collaboration with other RIA projects dealing with Citizen Science the structure and timeline of the newsletter were adapted. The strategy has been to introduce new RIAs in the newsletters and focus on certain topics for each of the newsletters. Meetings with RIAs are taking place regularly, on a monthly basis and support the knowledge exchange across projects.

Work package 6 still follows the aim to raise awareness of the potential of Citizen Science and achieve high visibility of EU-Citizen-Science and its engagement with all stakeholders, including researchers, practitioners, educators, policy makers, and the general public.

4.2. EU-Citizen.Science progress indicators

While the reflective talks with work package leaders served to get insight into the project's progress, identify challenges and important achievements in qualitative terms, we also defined a number of quantitative indicators that aim to keep track of the project's progress.

⁶ Webinar on the Characteristics of Citizen Science, <https://zenodo.org/record/3859970>

The following table (Table 1) is taken from D7.1 and shows target output numbers for the whole project duration. The actual numbers at the time of writing this deliverable are noted in the table, in brackets.

Table 1: EU-Citizen.Science KPIs

PLATFORM	TRAINING	RESOURCES	DISSEMINATION
total expected: 10,000 unique visitors current actual: 19,249 unique visitors	total expected: 20 training modules	total expected: 150 resources current actual: 88 resources, 145 projects	total expected: 150 attendees at final event in Brussels
total expected: 4,000 returning unique visitors current actual: 3,079 returning unique visitors	total expected: 4 target groups covered	total expected: 500 downloads actual numbers: 4,970 page views on resources, 3,178 page views on projects (we do link to resources e.g. on Zenodo or other websites, but do not offer them for download directly on our site)	total expected: 1,500 attendees at local and EU- wide events actual numbers: 3277 attendees at local and EU- wide events
total expected: >30 countries actual numbers: > 150 countries	total expected: User testing with 20 test persons, representing different target groups		total expected: 200 Followers Facebook actual numbers: 1592 Followers Facebook
total expected: 20,000 page visits actual numbers: 112,356 page visits			total expected: 2300 Followers Twitter actual numbers: 3521 Followers Twitter
total expected: >2 minutes average time spent on site actual numbers: 3:08 minutes average time per session			total expected: 520 Followers Instagram actual numbers: 650 Followers Instagram
total expected: user testing in 2 locations, 10 people each actual numbers: user testings in 3 locations, all together 19 people			total expected: 400 subscribers to newsletter actual number: 664 subscribers to newsletter
			total expected: 10 publications in journals and sector-specific magazines actual number: 24 including the newsletters

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			total expected: 35 presentations in external workshops/conferences/events actual number: 35 presentations in external workshops/ conferences/events
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5 Evaluation and interim impact of the EU-Citizen.Science Platform

5.1. User acceptance testing 1

The first user acceptance testing was organised at the end of March 2020, directly before the launch of the first version of the EU-Citizen.Science platform. Its aim was to collect feedback on the usability and perceived usefulness of the platform. Walkthroughs for the platform were organised, based on two scenarios that introduced two fictive personas and 4 tasks each on the platform. Test users were invited to choose one persona and go through the given tasks. After each task feedback forms were provided to collect immediate feedback concerning the respective task. At the end of the testing general usability and usefulness questions were posed to the testers.

Originally the user acceptance testing was foreseen as an event, where the test person would sit together with one person of the evaluation team and go through the scenario together, while thinking aloud. Due to the COVID-19 situation, the testing was transferred to the online world only. The results are presented hereafter.

Feedback Scenario 1:

Testing scenario 1 was performed by 5 people, all female researchers of different age groups (see figure 1):

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Please indicate your age:

5 responses

Figure 1: Age distribution of testers in scenario 1

Tasks 1: Look up practical guidelines on how to set up a Citizen Science project

This task was perceived differently by the testers. We received overall positive feedback on the navigation structure of the platform, but when it comes to looking for guidelines more specifically, the experiences were more diverse and some users faced difficulties. We asked testers to look for guidelines, but none of our resources that were online at the time of testing had „guideline“ in their title; as the search function was only searching in resources titles, searching for “guidelines” did not work. So for an easy solving of the task, users needed to find the filter option and choose the option “guidelines” there. Then all resources tagged as “guideline” would show up.

Suggestions were:

- to extend the search function to include full text
- to add the search function and main (filter) categories of our resources directly to the landing page.
- to use the overall menu for structuring content, e.g. by offering sub-menu items that include different resources types, like “guidelines”

Other remarks:

One tester came across the sign-in function, although this was not part of this task yet. And she wondered where she found information on the benefits of signing in. She suggests being more clear on this.

Task 2: Finding and comprehending a specific resource

In this task the testers-user had to look for a specific resource that was mentioned in the task-description. When testers took one word of the resource name and entered it to the search function, the right result was shown, so this task was easily completed.

Other remarks:

One tester wanted to rate the resource, but it did not work. And she said that the image of the resource was too big. She suggested using the same type of images for the same type of resource.

Task 3: Share a resource with others

In this task testers were invited to login (we provided them with user-id and password in the task description) and upload a specific resource that was provided via a link. In general they found the task of uploading a resource easy to do, once they found their way to the place where they could add a resource. The biggest problem was that that expected to upload resources from their profile page:

- „I first did not see where I can upload a resource; went to my profile and did not see an upload button there; then I went to resources and I had to look a bit to see the add button“,
- „I didn't see an "upload" button?“

Some testers faced difficulties with the required information for uploading a resource.

- “when entering the authors' names, as instructed I added a comma but that appears at the end of the name”
- "doi" => not every publication has a "doi" AND I was not able to add a new author!!

Suggestions were:

- that resources can also be uploaded from the profile page.
- that users can add new authors (comment: it is possible to add new authors, but this request from the user shows that she had problems to do so -> so we have checked that feature again).

Task 4: Edit the personal profile:

In this task testers were asked to add the profile information. This task was perceived differently. Some users completed it quickly and thought that it was great to have personal profiles on the platform.

One user reported about very concrete problems with adding an image and tags:

“I first selected an image that was probably too big, but the system did not tell me; it just did not upload the image; there should be a warning; also the tags I used as my interests did not work at first; only with the new image it also saved the interest tags; that was a bit strange. Several users said that they could not save anything in the interest area.”

Suggestions were:

- allowing to add an „alias“ to the profile.

Other remarks:

I liked the "geo-information" - very cool, if everybody is doing that - at the end we get a nice world-wide view

Feedback Scenario 2:

Scenario 2 had 7 complete responses, all from female testers, a majority being between 46 and 55 years old (see figure 2).

7 responses

Figure 2: Age distribution of testers in scenario 2

Task 1: Look up Citizen Science projects

The general feedback from testers on this task was good – they liked the straight-forward menu tabs, the search function, the way that results were displayed.

The only negative feedback was that:

- the search could not handle multiple word search
- the small number of listed projects
- and one person did not like the “cards” style of the project. She said that it does not allow to compare projects and therefore she would prefer a list.

One suggestion of improvement was to allow multiple countries to be added to a project or allow a European/worldwide perspective to be added.

Task 2: Finding a specific project

This task was perceived as being more difficult as we asked to find a project, which had a Spanish name, but testers - typed the english translation to the search and therefore it was not found.

We received diverging feedback concerning the presentation of the projects:

- I like the structure (headings like main info, geography, funding...)
- for me it is too much text, I would like to get much more information in tables or keywords
- no contact information provided for project; topic or tags for projects are not provided

Suggestions for improvement were:

- to make a full text search
- to open the link to the project in a new window so that users do not navigate away from the platform;
- to activate the rating feature;

Task 3: Share a resource with others

Some testers found this task simple, two had problems to log in and others faced two main challenges:

- to find the add-function for sharing a resource - it should be more visible and part of the “personal area” menu.
- to add specifics about the project; problems were specifically mentioned regarding the tagging function; that open fields are not long-enough; that text can not be formatted; that there is no pool of images to choose from when adding a project.

Task 4: Edit the personal profile

This task was generally perceived as being very easy.

One comment:

- Maybe I would like to arrange my resources and annotate them for me; so that could be a nice feature for the future

General feedback on the platform from both testgroups:

All testers said that they liked the “look and feel” of the platform, it was perceived as simple, pretty and professional.

The focus of the platform content on European projects and important resources was mentioned as positive as well. All users highlighted the value of having a European platform, where the community could share knowledge and resources and can add projects and resources.

Other remarks were:

- It is not clear whether I can perform my CS projects on the platform or whether it is solely a repository.
- I think it is super important to have curated content on the platform; so not everything should be there but the users should be pointed to really good and useful resources that have been applied in the past and have already been approved by others. Recommendations would be nice too.
- It needs a spell-check with entering information
- Is there a "place" where people can share "unstructured" knowledge, experiences, pictures, notes ... something "messy" but "lively" like a blackboard in a school
- I would like to see links to national Citizen Science platform and have all the e.g. Italian projects then there; or all the Spanish ones there;
- The project list should contain past Citizen Science projects too
- There should be information where the data is stored that is added to the personal account (location of server)
- Add at least "diverse" to the gender choice
- Include a map, where you can see 1) all CS projects 2) all users of the platform

Answers to the system usability questionnaire showed an overall positive feedback (fig 3).

Figure 3: Results of the System Usability Questionnaire first testing

5.2. User acceptance testing 2

The second user acceptance testing was organised at the end of September 2020, directly before the launch of the second version of the Eu-citizen.science platform. Its aim was to collect feedback on the new features introduced in this second release. With this aim, walkthroughs for the platform were organised. This time we did not create fictive personas, but asked test-users to go through specific tasks using their own background. This proceeding had the advantage that the testing was at the one hand very close to the testers real live experience and on the other hand helped to populate the platform. 4 tasks were described for the testers, after each task feedback forms were provided to collect immediate feedback concerning the respective task. At the end of the testing general usability and usefulness questions were posed to the testers. The results are presented here:

Feedback user acceptance testing 2

6 people conducted the second user acceptance testing, 2 of them male and 4 female, representing age groups between 26 and 55 years old.

Task 1: Register/login to the platform

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This task was easily completed by all test participants, only one participant stated that he/she could not upload a profile picture when creating a new user account.

Task 2: Search for all resources related to „evaluation“

We asked testers to describe how they approached this task. 4 testers typed evaluation in the search field, 2 testers went to the resources page and looked for a filter option for evaluation resources.

All of the testers found this task easy to complete. The ones who used the search function also were satisfied with the results shown. The ones who used the category “evaluation in Citizen Science” were less satisfied:

One person said: “I was hoping to find evaluation guidelines or something similar. It seems that most of the resources presented there are covering evaluation only in some parts.”

The other was not satisfied with the results from the evaluation filter and thus typed “evaluation” in the search field

Task 3: Search for all projects from Germany

All testers went to the project page and then selected the filter “Germany”. Unfortunately this filter function did not work properly for anyone.

One tester found a way around. She saw a project that had the tag “Germany”, clicked on this tag and saw all projects on the platform from Germany then.

We tried to reconstruct the error that was experienced by users, as the filter function for countries was technically working properly. We found out that when switching from the list of resources shown under task 2 to the project page, the search word “evaluation” was still kept in memory. So when test users in addition selected the filter “Germany”, only projects that were related to 1) Germany and to 2) evaluation appeared - in this case 0 projects. Would test users have cleared their search before, they would have seen the list of German projects on EU-Citizen.Science. We have to clarify how we can deal with this usability issue.

Task 4: Look, if your own organisation has already been added to EU-Citizen.Science

This task was approached by three testers by typing in the name of their organisation into the search field. 3 users went to the organisation page and applied the “country” filter there.

Problems were only reported by one tester: he started to type the name of his organisation to the search field - and the search function completed the entry by automatically showing the full name of the organisation. But when selecting this automatically generated full name of the organisation there was no result. Only when entering the name of the organisation and clicking on the “enter” the good result would show up.

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Task 5: Go to the Forum: Try to register there if you have not done that so far. Try to look for a topic of interest and subscribe.

This task showed that there are uncertainties on which levels users could subscribe to the forum. Exemplary comments are as follows:

- I went to the Forum and looked into the topic "The EU.Citizen.Science Project"; the "subscription" button is not clear to me; what exactly does it? when I clicked on it, it says : "topics that you are subscribed" - "no topics found" - when I subscribe the topic, why do I get the message, "no topics found"
- it is at first a bit confusing with the different forums and topics, e.g. not clear at which level one can subscribe

General feedback on the platform

In general the platform was once again described as being very clear, easy to orientate and down to what is needed; direct access to resources, projects, training, etc.

What was criticised is mainly the content and the forum, which is not perceived as being very appealing:

- There are still some inconsistencies in the data and this should be fixed; otherwise I will not find what I am looking for;
- the forum is also something that I need to get used to; it does not look and feel very appealing, but rather confusing at first with all the different labels

The results of the System Usability Scale (see Figure 4) show a more diverse picture than in the first testing. With increasing complexity also the complexity in navigation increases. Amongst the testers we had especially two who found that the different functionalities need to be better integrated - this feedback is mainly due to the forum plug-in and the errors experienced during the testing.

Figure 4: Results of the System Usability Questionnaire second testing

5.3. ECSA Conference Feedback

The ECSA Conference in September 2020 was foreseen as being one of the main events to collect feedback on the EU-Citizen.Science Platform. Due to the COVID-19 situation it was transferred to the online world, thus the opportunity to meet and talk with participants about the new platform was reduced. Next to the online workshop dedicated to the platform, four questions about EU-Citizen.Science were added to the final evaluation questionnaire, which was sent by the Conference organisers via e-mail to the 507 participants of the ECSA conference (including the organisers). The questionnaire was sent out in the first week of November and kept online for four weeks, by which point no one new was responding.

In the following we present the results of this questionnaire that was answered by 106 participants and the exact number of answers to each question are always indicated in the diagrams below.

How often have you accessed the EU-Citizen.Science platform so far?

The first question aimed to collect the participants' frequency of accessing the new platform, also as a baseline for comparison in the upcoming years. Figure 5 shows that only 10% out of 106 participants have never accessed the platform, while 23% have accessed it once. The largest group of participants (50% of participants) has accessed EU-Citizen.Science a few times. We find only a small number of users though, who have accessed the platform in regular terms.

How often have you accessed the EU-Citizen.Science platform so far? (n=106)

Figure 5: Access to the EU-Citizen.Science platform

How useful have you found the EU-Citizen.Science platform so far?

The answers to this question are visualised in Figure 6. 22 of 102 participants said that they have never used the platform - the difference to the 10 people having indicated that they have never accessed the platform in the question before might be due to the fact that 12 people have once accessed the platform, but not actually used it. Nearly a third of participants thought that the platform was “somewhat useful”, another third rated it as being “useful” and 11 users - being 10% or respondents - evaluated it as very useful. So we think that this result is satisfying for the time being and we expect that these usefulness perceptions will improve as the number of resources, projects, training modulus, and the forum features also increase.

Figure 6: Perceived usefulness of the EU-Citizen.Science platform

What have been your most important activities on the platform?

In the third question we wanted to know from participants what was their most important activity on the platform. To answer this question respondents were allowed to choose one option only. The answers (see Figure 7) show that searching for resources and projects are the most important activities for the 102 respondents, with 36% of participants searching for resources and 33% searching for projects. Reading news/blog entries is for 13% the most important activity while 4% said that they used the platform most importantly to share their own resources. These results are also backed with numbers from the access statistics presented below. Projects and resources are currently the most important content elements of our platform and we will see how far this changes with an increasing number of training modules and also the interactive features of the forum, which have only been launched in September 2020, being more established.

What have been your most important activities on the platform? (n=80)

Figure 7: Most important activities on the EU-Citizen.Science platform

What is the most important objective of the EU-Citizen.Science platform?

The final question had an open-ended format and was answered by 24 participants. The most important objectives of the platform can be summarized as follows:

- *To become a central place for resources on Citizen Science (toolkits, handbooks, webinars, courses, fresh ideas), well selected, reliable and curated.*
- *To provide access to and connect Citizen Science projects and activities in Europe.*
- *To be a place for networking, also bringing together academics and practitioners*
- *To become a place for knowledge exchange and sharing of experiences*

5.4. Platform access statistics:

The access statistics are a rich source of information that help us to better understand the interests and needs of the Citizen Science community and also show the acceptance of the website amongst the community, if we succeed to have steady or slowly growing access rates from different countries in Europe.

So first we will investigate which content was most accessed. Then we will look into the users accessing our website.

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The following data represent the period from 6th of April 2020 (the launch date of the platform) until the 17th of November 2020 (the day of writing this chapter). The data are extracted from Google-Analytics:

Figure 8: Development of page views on the EU-Citizen.Science platform

Figure 8 shows the development of page views over time. We can see a steady pattern of page views, being low on week-end and higher during week-days, especially from Tuesday to Thursday. While the page views have been lower in the summer months of July and August (ranging between 250 and 350 during the weekdays), they considerably increased at the time of the ECSA conference with a specific peak on September, 8th, where the new features of the platform have been introduced to conference participants. Also after the ECSA conference page views stayed a bit higher than before with 550-850 during week-days. Platform users spent an average time of 1:12 minutes on a page.

Homepage (26,637 page views / unique 18,963 page views):

As expected the homepage is the most frequently accessed page of our platform. It has so far gathered nearly 19,000 unique page views, which means the number of sessions during which the homepage was viewed at least once. Overall the homepage was viewed more than 26,000 times, where repeated views of a single page during one session are counted.

Projects overview site (8,085 page views/ unique 4697 pageviews):

The project overview site is the most accessed site on our platform directly after the homepage. The difference between unique pageviews and pageviews, shows that users returned back to the project overview during their session - which means they accessed this page more than one time during a session.

At the time of writing this deliverable, the platform profiles 145 Citizen Science projects. Specifically: 4 from Belgium, 1 from Denmark, 6 from Germany, 4 from Estland, 3 from France, 1 from Ghana, 5 from Greece, 3 from Ireland, 1 from Israel, 9 from Italy, 1 from Lithuania, 9 from the Netherlands, 1 from Norway, 8 from Austria, 9 from Portugal, 1 from Romania, 11 from Sweden, 3 from Switzerland, 1 from Senegal, 31 from Spain, 1 from the Czech Republic, 5 from Hungaria, 6 from the United States, 18 from the UK.

The form to upload a new project was opened 662 times.

The most accessed Projects so far are (altogether the single project pages have 10,106 page views / 8,203 unique page views):

Table 2: Most accessed projects on the EU-Citizen.Science platform

Folding@Home - Coronavirus	538 / unique 488
FoldIt: Quarantine Edition	517/ unique 441
The Ladybird Experiment	326 / unique 186
Micromascotas	308 / unique 99
Crowd4SDG	222/ unique 206
The Global Healthsites Mapping project	205 / unique 186

The first two projects in the table 2 are also listed first, when users select the menu-item “projects”.

But nevertheless, it is an interesting mix of themes: While the Folding@Home and the FoldIt projects address health research, The Ladybird Experiment and Micromascotas projects address biodiversity. The last two are projects in the social domain.

Resources overview site (4511 page views / unique 2670 page views):

The starting page for resources is one of the most important sites on our platform. Again, the comparison between page views and unique page views shows that people returned back to the resources overview site during their session.

Overall 88 resources are profiled on EU-Citizen.Science at the time of writing this deliverable (7 in German, 64 in English, 6 in Spanish, 1 in Estonian, 2 in French, 3 in Hungarian, 1 in Italian, 1 in Lithuanian, 2 in Dutch, 1 in Portuguese).

The most accessed resources so far are (altogether the single resource pages have 4,970 page views / 4,326 unique page views) :

Table 3: Most accessed resources on the EU-Citizen.Science platform

The ECSA Characteristics of Citizen Science	455 page views / unique 404
ECSA 10 principles of Citizen Science	376 page views / unique 345 (high access rates especially in the last months)
Guide to Citizen Science - developing, implementing and evaluating Citizen Science to study biodiversity and the environment in the UK	253 page views/ unique 235 (high access rates especially in the last months)
The Spotteron Citizen Science Platform	213 page views/ unique 188 (this resource had very high access rates in the beginning but this decreased then steadily)

Socientize White Paper on Citizen Science in Europe	164 page views/ unique 154 (high access rates especially in the last months)
Citizen Science Projects: How to Make a Difference	163 page views / unique 157
The Challenge of Evaluation: An Open Framework for Evaluating Citizen Science Activities	145 page views/ unique 127
Citizen Science for all. A Guide for Citizen Science practitioners	127 page views/ unique 122 (high access rates especially in the last months)

As table 3 shows, participants either search for resources that help them better understand Citizen Science as a general approach (e.g. The ECSA Characteristics of Citizen Science and The 10 principles of Citizen Science documents), or they look for practical information on how to conduct and evaluate Citizen Science activities. The form to add a new resource was viewed 267 times.

Forum (4,004 page views / 2,545 unique page views)

Interestingly the forum has already a high number of page views, although it is online since September 2020 only and has very low contributions from users. We observe a peak during the ECSA Conference, especially on the day the new platform features were presented to the community. The high number of page views shows us that there is interest, but we have not succeeded so far to motivate active participation.

The most often accessed topics were:

- The European Green Deal funding call - interest in partnerships? (20 contributions, 227 page views / 182 unique page views)
- National and Regional CS Networks (176 / 108 unique page views)

Login (page views 1,487 / 726 unique page views) / Users' personal profile page (2,896 page views/ 1,798 unique page views)

We currently have 662 users with an active account. The login screen was accessed 1,487 times. The personal profile page that opens when users have once logged in (or stayed logged in) was accessed nearly 3,000 times. So we see that the registered users of our platform are very active.

About (2,790 / 2,188 unique page views)

The About page where we introduce the EU-Citizen.Science project and project partners was viewed 2,790 times. For a period of 7 months this number is considerable, so people are also interested in who is standing behind the platform.

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Citizen Science Resources during the COVID-19 Pandemic (2,477page views / 2,323 unique page views)

This page was created during the first lockdown of the COVID-19 pandemic in spring 2020 and presented a number of Citizen Science activities that can be done from home. The high number of page views was created between the 6th of April and the 15th of May only, and shows the potential of the platform to stimulate emergent activities with relevance for the users.

Our Gold Star Selection (2,029 page views / 1,548 unique page views)

The starting page of our curated resources has steady page views over the whole period and demonstrates the users' interest in what we as consortium perceive as high quality resources.

Blog (2,112 page views / 1,808 unique page views)

Our blog offers edited articles (normally between 3 to 5 per month, in the summer months a bit less) about new initiatives, projects, events, training, etc. in the Citizen Science community and shows a steady number of page views over the whole period. Thus highlighting the communities' interest in this edited contributions from consortium patterns or invited experts from outside of the consortium.

Next to the COVID-19-Pandemic page and the Citizen Science Characteristics page the most important blog-entries were:

- Tips and Tricks for Hosting a Successful Collaborative Online Meeting (159 page views / 147 unique page views)
- An Introduction to the FAIR principles (126 page views / 116 unique page views)

Organisations (1,139 page views / 515 unique page views)

Since September 2020 platform users can also add their organisations, if they are active in Citizen Science. In the two months 59 organisations have been added to the platform and the entry page has had more than 1000 views. So it seems that this is a very well appreciated new feature.

The form to add a new organisation was viewed 286 times in this short period.

The organisations that were most often viewed are the ones that are also found on top of the list:

- ECSA (250 page views / 83 unique page views),
- Ibercivis (134 page views / 78 unique page views) and
- Ecsite (72 page views / 9 unique page views).

Users of the platform

Figure 9: Development of numbers of users on the EU-Citizen.Science platform

The overview chart, Figure 9, shows a high number of users during workdays after the launch of the platform, a decrease in numbers of using our platform during summer months and another rise from end of August until the time of writing this deliverable. We see a peak of users between the 25th and 27th of August - in this time we had a high number of new users from Spain accessing our platform, which is due to a tweet of the Spanish ministry of science and innovation on the 25th. We have 618 new users in these three days, 418 of them coming from Spain. Another rise in numbers of users can be observed during the ECSA conference from 8th to 10th September, another the following week during the Austrian Citizen Science Conference on the 16th of December and one more on the 23rd of September. So we see that dissemination efforts via online conferences and social media have an influence on users accessing our platform.

Figure 10: Age of the EU-Citizen.Science platform users

The age distribution, Figure 10, shows that users between 25 and 34 represent the biggest group on our platform. We have 57,1% female users and 42,9% male.

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Looking at the different users accessing our pages, we get interesting insights especially into the interests from different European countries. The following table 4 shows the number of users, sessions and pages/sessions from different countries, starting with the highest numbers.

Table 4: EU-Citizen.Science platform users according to European countries

Country	Users	Sessions	Pages/session
Spain	3,607	6,756	5.24
Germany	1,622	2,973	3.70
United Kingdom	1,387	2,227	3.11
Italy	1,345	2,070	3.33
Netherlands	1,044	1,532	3.05
Belgium	922	1,561	3.24
France	865	1,318	4.31
Austria	617	1,031	4.72
Portugal	566	926	3.40
Finland	490	591	1.87
Greece	451	832	3.50
Switzerland	311	477	3.13
Sweden	262	506	3.94
Ireland	261	382	3.01
Romania	204	293	3.56
Poland	196	276	2.95
Hungary	188	464	4.00
Denmark	176	265	3.15
Slovenia	140	174	3.06
Turkey	131	196	2.18
Czechia	107	136	3.17
Norway	99	149	3.24
Serbia	86	132	2.98
Lithuania	71	112	3.22
Croatia	59	77	2.82
Slovakia	51	90	2.47
Bulgaria	50	63	2.76
Ukraine	48	62	2.05
Cyprus	44	68	2.34
Estonia	41	66	3.83
Latvia	34	58	1.71
Luxembourg	30	36	3.61

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So we have certainly high interest from countries where Citizen Science as a scientific approach is already well established and supported - like Spain, Germany, Great Britain (more on this will be presented below as result from the interviews). But we also see interest from countries where Citizen Science is still in its infancy, like Lithuania, Ukraine, and Estonia.

Interesting is also that countries that do not have national Citizen Science platforms, yet, such as Italy, Greece, Portugal, Sweden, and Ireland show high numbers of users on our platform.

The following table, Table 5, presents the user numbers from outside of Europe; on top the United States with a very high number of users and sessions.

Table 5: EU-Citizen.Science platform users outside of Europe

Country	Users	Sessions	Pages/session
United States	1,585	1,711	1.46
Brazil	181	266	2.93
Australia	163	244	2.57
China	158	162	1.63
India	142	175	2.42
Argentina	134	169	3.42
Israel	126	231	4.90
Mexico	124	137	2.34
Canada	88	101	1.76
Russia	83	102	3.29
Japan	79	97	2.28
Chile	65	81	3.31
Philippines	62	119	1.52
Colombia	59	82	2.59
South Korea	52	81	3.59
Peru	36	62	4.08

6 Organisational impact across partners and beyond

In the following we summarize the interviews that were conducted with partners and third parties of the EU-Citizen.Science project in December 2019. In total, this summary is based on 14 interviews with representatives of partner organisations based across Europe.

6.1 Current Citizen Science Landscape

The recognition of Citizen Science as a scientific method varies largely across the partner organisations and across their countries.

Citizen Science in organisations

Partner interviews showed that the organisational commitment towards Citizen Science varies a lot across organisations in Europe. In some cases Citizen Science has been recognised as a strategic objective and is thus given structural support in the form of funding for Citizen Science activities or the establishment of Citizen Science labs. While in other partner organisations Citizen Science is still driven by the personal interest of individuals, without any specific organisational support.

Good examples where the cooperation between volunteers and researchers has a long tradition are the Natural History Museums, such as in France, UK, Germany, Belgium, Italy or Estonia. In these partner organisations Citizen Science has often found its way into the museums' science and science communication strategies. Some of these partners are not only actively involved in Citizen Science projects themselves, they also provide their expertise on how to conduct Citizen Science to other organisations, becoming central players for Citizen Science in their countries.

However, within this group of museums we find structural differences. While in some institutions the volunteers' engagement is organised under the umbrella of "Citizen Science" for many years, in others the understanding of their volunteer activities as "Citizen Science" is quite recent. In some we find dedicated staff responsible for the Citizen Science agendas, in others Citizen Science is supported in looser working groups and networks that are composed of representatives from different scientific domains. Some museums are closely linked to universities in enacting and funding their Citizen Science activities, others are organising their activities independently. One example for the former case is the Natural History Museum in Paris, which has a close collaboration with the Sorbonne University. Together they offer a platform⁷ for around 34 Citizen Science projects, where users can also find resources on Citizen Science; and they plan to open a Citizen Science competence centre, where project owners from the university are assisted in developing their own Citizen Science projects.

Another group of partner organisations are those that are explicitly dedicated to deepening the link between science and society. In these organisations Citizen Science is regarded as one amongst several approaches to reach this aim. These organisations are either organised as non-profit research institutes, or like in the case of the Spanish partner FECYT, as a public body. Supporting Citizen Science activities has a long tradition and is explicitly done via projects, training workshops, platforms or, in the latter case even via a dedicated funding programme that spent e.g. 300.000 Euro on Citizen Science projects in 2019.

The landscape of Citizen Science activities and support amongst academic partners, mostly universities, is comparable to the other institutes, very heterogeneous and shows a very diverse picture. We have universities that provide a Citizen Science Lab (e.g. University

⁷ <https://www.science-ensemble.org/>

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Leiden in the Netherlands⁸) or a central researcher service department that effectively supports their staff in setting up Citizen Science projects, acquiring funding for their activities, organises workshops and trainings, etc. Although these structures seem to be well established, their staffing, which tends to be 1-2 persons, and resources has to be re-negotiated regularly. The BOKU in Austria e.g. is even hosting the national platform for Citizen Science with a committed budget from the university. In other universities the involvement in Citizen Science activities is driven by individual academics or departments, without any formal structure at hand. In this case, volunteer participation in research may have a long tradition, or be a completely new topic, depending on the location of the university. Funding via projects is of high importance here to keep activities alive and continue raising awareness for Citizen Science. At an institutional level, Citizen Science often has not found it's ways into university strategies yet, but is linked to outreach and science communication, which is encouraged in all universities.

Finally, one third party of our consortium is part of a municipality. The MFCR(MUNICIPIO RODRIGO DE FIGUEIRA DE CASTELO) in Portugal aims to establish Citizen Science initiatives sustainably in the municipality via an innovation office that links citizens, who bring in their concerns, and researchers, who help to address these concerns with their scientific expertise. Again, sustainable funding for these activities is something that needs to be negotiated regularly.

Overall, the importance of Citizen Science has been growing. Even in the organisations where Citizen Science has not yet been a strategic priority it is gaining visibility and interest. This has been confirmed especially by partners from Central and Eastern Europe, such as Hungary, Estonia and Lithuania. Entry points towards Citizen Science are either specific departments, European projects, such as H2020 projects (e.g. DITOS⁹), or established networks outside the organisation. There are some that have less internal support, but strong collaborations with other European institutions, such as AUTH (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki)¹⁰ from Greece, who has been working in collaboration with Saarland University (Germany) and Aarhus University (Denmark) in the field of participatory air quality sensing and are offering joint trainings for industry and academics. A similar entry point to Citizen Science has been reported by the Portuguese partner, who - as part of a local municipality - got involved in a cross national collaboration of open science hubs with the University Leiden¹¹ where Citizen Science practices were applied to tackle local relevant challenges in a participatory manner. And the small Italian history museum started their Citizen Science activities via a collaboration with OPAL in the UK¹².

While there are already many established links for Citizen Science collaborations that go back many years, some partners were pointing towards a need for more collaboration and exchange across Europe (e.g. France).

⁸ <https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/citizensciencelab>

⁹ <http://www.togetherscience.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://www.auth.gr>

¹¹ <https://www.scishops.eu/visit-to-open-science-hub-in-portugal/>

¹² <http://www.museonaturalemamma.it/>

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Citizen Science at national level

The diversity of attention and commitment that Citizen Science is receiving at the organisational level we also see reflected in the national landscape. There are frontrunners such as Austria¹³, Germany¹⁴ or Spain¹⁵, who have established national platforms for Citizen Science, or France, who has a national resource centre for all professionals involved in Citizen Science. We also came across some cross-national initiatives, such as the platform in Flemish¹⁶, which is offering projects from Belgium and the Netherlands or national platforms that are specifically dedicated to bundling and promoting certain types of Citizen Science, such as biodiversity, ornithology, etc. Some national portals, such as the Swedish or the Lithuanian, are just now being established.

On the other side of the spectrum, our partner organisations from e.g. Central and Eastern Europe report that central support structures for Citizen Science are still in their infancy or not existing yet. However, awareness for Citizen Science is growing and potentially this may also lead to a more coordinated approach. Similar developments and a growing interest has been reported from partners in the South of Europe, such as Greece, Italy, or Portugal.

Formalisation of support for Citizen Science activities is on-going. In some countries formal structures have already been established in the form of associations, as public bodies or as initiatives financed by a leading university, offering services beyond their institution. Other countries are starting to build such structures. And finally there are some cases where Citizen Science infrastructures are not being considered a priority yet (e.g. Ireland, Greece).

For some of the partners, the ECSA working group of national platforms¹⁷ is an important initiative to share experiences across countries. In addition, the German speaking countries have an established collaboration for many years, where they exchange their experiences in cross-national working groups and this exchange should be intensified in the coming years.

We encounter that networking and structuring activities at the national level often depend on the strong commitment of individuals and informal groups, such as in Portugal, where they organise meetings, knowledge exchange and even a conference, bringing together around 150 people across the country without any formal support structures. So far, national coordination activities mostly depend on personal engagement, but we clearly noticed a wish to institutionalize structures, in this specific case at the municipality, but servicing across the country. EU-Citizen.Science is regarded as a great opportunity to advance with the professionalization of Citizen Science at the country level.

Some countries have already established National Citizen Science conferences, such as Austria or Portugal. And here we also see that these initially are driven by the strong commitment of individuals.

¹³ <https://www.citizen-science.at/>

¹⁴ <https://www.buergerschaftenwissen.de/>

¹⁵ <https://ciencia-ciudadana.es/>

¹⁶ <https://www.iedereenwetenschapper.be/>

¹⁷ <https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/working-groups/citizen-science-networks/>

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In a number of countries our partners report about national funding programmes for Citizen Science, such as Austria, Germany, UK, or Spain. The latter is especially interesting as the funding organisation, a public foundation under the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities, itself is a partner in the EU-Citizen.Science project (FECYT). Spain is an example where policy makers at national level have realised the importance of Citizen Science and are strategically engaged in the EU-Citizen.Science project.

From our public organisations we hear however also that governmental support may be volatile and support may change with each election or changes in the governing structures and personnel.

Our partners are all well aware of the value that Citizen Science has at national level and they are connected across their countries with entities that are likewise practicing and/or promoting Citizen Science.

Across Europe, Citizen Science is gaining momentum, across the countries, but there is still a lot to be done in terms of awareness, incentives, support structures and funding mechanisms. This applies to all stakeholders: for example, in many countries our partners still estimate the percentage of academic staff being aware of Citizen Science methods as very low. Only some countries have established permanent structures in universities, such as central offices with dedicated staff, who function as Citizen Science contact centres. But even in the countries where universities have support structures we hear from our partners that Citizen Science is not very common across academia. Important national Citizen Science stakeholders are NGOs, who have Citizen Science activities at their core, such as Birdlife International¹⁸.

Citizen Science is often promoted together with science communication and is partially benefitting from the push of science communication, public engagement and dissemination at the European level. This has been taken up by universities and research institutions across Europe and is also reflected in more attention being paid to public engagement. However, funding the activities is often an issue as e.g. the Estonian partner reports that there is no funding for science communication and thus no incentives. Other partners associate the emergence of their Citizen Science activities with their connection to science shops and living labs (Hungary, Sweden).

In terms of content, BioBlitzes and citizen observatories have been mentioned various times as activities with most visibility across the country and addressing different target groups, e.g. school children and adults. Similarly, in Sweden Citizen Science started to get wide public attention via mass experiments with schools that have been taken up by mass media and are now well known across the country. Also in Ireland, environmental monitoring is dominating in Citizen Science activities, with the Environmental Protection Agency being the national champion in Citizen Science with their own website of projects that they run and plans to turn this into the national Citizen Science portal for Ireland.

The term Citizen Science turned out to be problematic in some countries, as it either does not have an appropriate translation or the term causes different connotations. Hungary is such a case, where Citizen Science is hard to communicate, the term itself is not translatable and

¹⁸ <https://www.birdlife.org/>

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people have a different concept of citizenship. So they need to work with other terms, such as community-based research, which creates additional messiness and unease around the concept. Another example would be Sweden, where there are a lot of Citizen Science activities going on, but they are often not labelled as such, as the term in Swedish is cumbersome to enunciate and does not transmit the same concepts as the English term does. The same was reported from the Netherlands., where most practitioners prefer to use the English term instead.

The need for a definition and quality criteria for Citizen Science was raised by some partners. The work initiated in WP2 on the characteristics for Citizen Science was perceived as an important step towards delineating Citizen Science from related practices.

6.2 Current Citizen Science activities (relevant for EU-Citizen.Science)

During the interviews our partners mentioned a set of highly relevant activities that they are already carrying out.

Training

A number of partners are providing training activities, either at organisational, local or national level. The training is mostly targeting researchers and activity leaders, guiding them on how to engage the specific target groups and how to run BioBlitzes (E.g.The National History Museum in London). The Italian partner also offers training in the context of BioBlitzes on biodiversity, as well as a more general training course on Citizen Science. The French National Museum of Natural History has a one-week-course for young researchers, including Citizen Science practices. Fecyt in Spain is offering training for their national scientific community, organised via their national network and a central workshop planned for 2020. The Austrian Citizen Science network is offering training for specific topics, such as legal aspects, ethics, etc. Our Irish partner offers training across the university for staff members. And finally, the German-speaking countries Austria, Germany and Switzerland also offer joint training/workshops.

Events

A diversity of Citizen Science related events are organised or co-organised by partner organisations. The most often mentioned events/activities are BioBlitzes. Partners are also organising national events for the Citizen Science community, such as in Spain, Germany or Austria, with their respective national Citizen Science conferences. In addition many partners organise outreach and science communication events, especially the science communication partners or the Museums. Presence at European Researchers' Night or similar national science communication activities are typical. The Austrian BOKU is experimenting with new formats to reach new groups of citizens via public adult education centers.

Networking

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An important activity for many partners is cross-organisational and cross-national collaboration and exchange. The networking activities range from very informal exchange of experiences to joint projects, programmes or activities, such as Open Science Hub that started as a cooperation between a local municipality in Portugal and the University in Leiden and then turned into a H2020 funded project.

Overall, our partners are well connected globally, with some being part of the Citizen Science global partnership or having established networks beyond Europe with other Citizen Science communities and actors.

Stakeholder target groups

Interviewees were asked which stakeholders they mostly address with their Citizen Science related activities. Taking all partners together the project has access to all relevant stakeholder groups, however, not in all countries equally.

The easiest to reach target group is clearly the scientific community as all partners have established ties with other researchers and scientists, universities and scientific institutions. However, the disciplines may vary, with a potentially greater access to the scientific community active in biodiversity.

Next to scientists our partners mention NGOs and amateur naturalist groups (e.g. via National History Museums) or people who already have some affinity to a certain topic as those where they have established contacts.

The general public is clearly not a focus for all partners, but e.g. for the partner organisations in the Netherlands, Belgium, and Sweden science communication is a core aspect and they address the general public with their activities. Similarly all the Museums that have been interviewed aim to address a wide audience across the general public.

The specific target group of schools/teachers has been mentioned by partners from the Netherlands (secondary schools), Belgium, Sweden and Portugal.

Among the target group of policy makers our partners mostly mention Ministries or local community administration and municipalities. The contact with Ministries is considered important to advance the topic of Citizen Science at national level, especially in those countries where there is not a clear national strategy, yet. For example, the Lithuania partner is in contact with the Ministry responsible for science and wants to focus on public officials in their dissemination effort in order to promote Citizen Science. In Italy, similarly, our partner wants to get in contact with the Ministries to get national support and push for a national Citizen Science strategy. Local municipalities are especially relevant stakeholders in Greece and Portugal. In Ireland, the Environmental Protection Agency is a core partner when it comes to promoting Citizen Science at the policy level, and they are a key stakeholder.

6.3 Expectations for EU-Citizen.Science

Interviewed partners were asked about their expectations with regards to their engagement in the project and in general, what EU-Citizen.Science should achieve.

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Reputation was mentioned as a core motivation to being part of the project in the first place; the participation in the international EU-Citizen.Science project that involves so many key players of Citizen Science across Europe increases the partners' standing in their countries and gives more weight for the national initiatives they take to foster Citizen Science.

Thus, the involvement in EU-Citizen.Science is understood as leverage for national activities, supporting communication activities for awareness raising on Citizen Science, to mainstream, to increase training, to increase interest in Citizen Science. Although limited, the project's financial support also contributes to the organisation of events that would not have been possible without the European funding. The EU-Citizen.Science platform also addresses a larger group of stakeholders than some national platforms do (e.g. it addresses not only researchers but also the broader public and policy makers)

Being part of the EU-Citizen.Science project also means being close to important information, resources, and experiences within the European network. Thus, building up own competencies, getting new inputs, ideas, and material is another important expectation from the project. With their participation the project partners expect to be able to better support their stakeholder groups, who are interested or involved in Citizen Science in their countries. Also getting input on how to better teach Citizen Science methods or seeking concrete exchange with other consortium partners on specific topics was mentioned as potentially highly beneficial. Examples in this respect are e.g. the exchange of experiences on BioBlitzes (an intense period of biological surveying in an attempt to record all the living species within a designated area) organised in different countries; good practices of air quality monitoring; examples for Citizen Science projects in the social sciences; and understanding the context of other countries and how Citizen Science is best supported via funding, but also how national platforms or associations are handled, etc.

There were also very concrete ideas on what kind of resources are expected on the platform to better support Citizen Science initiatives in the different European countries. These were for instance:

- Guidelines on how to start a Citizen Science project.
- Guidelines on how to engage citizen scientists and keep their involvement high.
- Best practice for Citizen Science in different domains.
- Useful and well curated tools for Citizen Science.
- A list of all national platforms and networks for Citizen Science.

When talking about these resources on the platform, especially for those countries that do not have national platforms yet, the language of the provided material becomes an important issue.

Partners suggested translating parts of the content to their mother tongue, or to involve stakeholders at an early stage in the translation of resources and training material (e.g. Italian, Greek, Hungarian, Lithuanian, Estonian).

The exchange of experiences - good and bad practices - was not only perceived as being important between partners, but also between the wider Citizen Science community. It is expected that via the platform we are able to overcome barriers of mutual learning that are

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due to different cultures and languages and partners can take the opportunity to benefit from Europe's diversity. In this regard a forum was suggested as one potential functionality of the platform. Generally, the online exchange and collaboration was also highlighted as an important alternative to physical presence, especially in times of climate change and scarce budgets.

The network not only supports the experience exchange between members of the community. It also allows to invite promoters of Citizen Science from countries, where Citizen Science is already more established, to introduce the idea of Citizen Science during national activities, as for instance done following the Vilnius meeting.

Very concrete success indicators that some partners have defined for their engagement in EU-Citizen.Science are for example:

- To have one national project in Lithuania that is dealing with Citizen Science at the end of the project, as a research subject or as a process.
- To have one go-to-place for information about Citizen Science in Lithuania.
- To have more Hungarian institutions joining ECSA.
- To have one European Citizen Science project, where people in different countries are involved in e.g. one European BioBlitz.

6.4 Engagement in EU-Citizen.Science

The interviews also aimed to find out how far our partners are already aware of where and how they can best engage and contribute to the project. Most are still in a waiting position.

In general, partners stressed that leading such a big consortium is certainly a challenge especially at the beginning and emphasized the openness of the project that allowed them to keep up to date if they wanted to, accessing the shared folder or contacting the coordinators or consortium partners in the case of questions.

But most interviewees also referred to the very small budgets they have and the need to invest this budget wisely to those tasks where their input is required most.

It seems that direct communication with them was low at the beginning of the project, keeping smaller partners and third parties rather in a waiting position until there was more clear instruction on how to get involved.

Several partners noted that it was perceived as very helpful, when work package leaders sent out an email with a concrete request for help and input. The work initiated in WP2 on the characteristics for Citizen Science, including the whole process of the vignette study, was mentioned several times in this regard, as an example for a clear task on how to support the project. For some partners having this small role was fine, others mentioned that it would be good to feel more connected to the project.

Concrete suggestions on how to improve their involvement were:

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Working groups: Foster the experience exchange between the consortium partners on topics of most relevance for them. Working groups could be initiated that are not as big as work packages, but aim to collect different opinions, resources and experiences from partners on a specific topic (e.g. BioBlitzes, mainstreaming Citizen Science in countries, strategies for achieving governmental engagement, Citizen Science in social sciences).

Concrete tasks and timeline for testing the platform & resources: most partners are aware that they should participate in the testing of the platform and the resources (also with the stakeholders they have at hand). But they would wish for a concrete timeline when to do that and also instructions, how to do that.

Concrete communication from work packages on how to get involved: if partners are requested to provide their input to specific work packages this request should come either via email or via a monthly meeting for third parties only, that provides a quick and concrete update on what happens in the project and where to contribute.

Travel budget: nearly all interviewees mentioned the small budget for traveling and that it would be good to have at least the budget to participate in all consortium meetings. With COVID-19 travel restrictions this has become less relevant, but is important for future funding reference.

In the following we have listed specific knowledge, material etc. that partners mentioned as relevant resources for the others and that could be shared via the platform:

- MNHN has a strong experience in building communities in Citizen Science and they want to share that.
- MFCR can bring in their experiences on how to use Citizen Science data for local public policy and also how to bring it to schools
- RINBS have organised BioBlitzes in the last two years and would be ready to share their experiences on that. The same is true for the UT, MRU, NHM. FGC has a report on their BioBlitzes in Italian language and translates the most important parts to English.
- AUTH is working together with the ECSA group on Air Quality Monitoring on Guidelines for how to start Citizen Science projects measuring air quality, what to consider etc. This could be provided to the platform. AUTH would also be ready to create material in the local language as this is perceived as being important.
- FGC has material in Italian language from their courses on Citizen Science.
- Fecyt has already organised workshops on Citizen Science, so maybe some of the material offered in these workshops can also be shared on the EU-Citizen.Science platform.
- ESSRG: has a review about Citizen Science on youtube <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=O4xdKenrIJ4&t=2s>

7 Summary, conclusion and outlook

Qualitative reflections, and quantitative indicators, show that the projects' progress is advancing as planned and we have collected interesting insights into the establishment of Citizen Science in the numerous partner organisations and countries.

The work packages have faced several challenges while trying to meet their objectives; challenges related to the different expectations coming from the broad range of target groups involved in Citizen Science, the broad range of opinions about what Citizen Science is and is not, the different understandings of what quality means related to resources on Citizen Science, the COVID-19 situation and resulting constraints in all European countries. Although some of these challenges are still pertinent, the overall performance of the project is well advancing. The KPIs are promising and show that we can expect to reach or even exceed them in the final project year.

Cross-work package discussions and activities related to the elaboration of the Characteristics of Citizen Science and definition of quality criteria for resources set an important groundwork for the consortium and the whole Citizen Science community at large.

Next to this definition work, the focus of the past years' activities was the development, testing and implementation of the EU-Citizen.Science portal. Two user acceptance tests (one in March 2020 before the initial launch and one in September 2020 before the second release) revealed some important bugs and usability issues that were considered by the technical team. The results of 19 tests showed the very positive feedback concerning the platforms' usefulness. Testers thought that a European place for Citizen Science resources and projects was highly valuable. Also the overall design and structure of the platform was perceived as appealing and clear.

The access numbers to our platform are satisfying and partly excel our expectations. We reached 20,000 unique visitors already in the first 8 months since the launch of the platform.

A questionnaire, which was sent to ECSA conference participants showed that only 10% of the more than 100 respondents have never accessed the platform, so we see that the community is to a large extent aware of the new platform. We have on average 85 new users every day on the platform, which is an important figure as we hope that our user community keep growing steadily. What we aim for is a higher number of returning visitors. Currently we count 18% of returning visitors. As we plan to continually extend the content offered on the platform (e.g. with new resources, training modulus etc.) we expect this number of returning visitors to grow.

Users showed a high interest in projects and resources - this is what both the questionnaire and the access statistics show. We find that the most important resources are those that either help to frame Citizen Science as a research approach, e.g. the ECSA Characteristics and The Ten Principles of Citizen Science; or practical guidelines that support the implementation and evaluation of Citizen Science activities. Interestingly, the number of projects profiled on our platform is exceeding the number of resources; also a high number of organisations have been added to the portal, which is possible since the second release in September only. So perhaps

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the platform is perceived as an opportunity to promote ones' organisation and projects, not so much as an opportunity to share resources.

We still miss users rating and commenting on the resources and projects. These ratings should help to define the quality of content on our platform. While the Citizen Science community expects to find high quality resources on the platform, they are still not aware of the fact that they are the ones to contribute these resources and to define with their comments and ratings what "high quality" means for them. As an example, the introduction to the ECSA Characteristics of Citizen Science has been accessed 450 times and we know from the feedback in discussion rounds and interviews how well this document is perceived - nevertheless there is only one rating. So platform users would not automatically know how excellent this resource is. Also the forum, which was launched in September, still needs time and efforts to make this an actively used feature. So there is more community building requested around the platform for the final project year.

Another interesting observation is that we had especially high page views on the list of selected projects that are doable at home during the first COVID-19 lockdown. This content was an immediate response of the consortium to the new situation and shows the power that the platform has in reaching out to the community, if the content is of relevance and covers actual needs.

In general, the COVID-19 crisis has clearly had an effect on the project activities, but not only in a negative way. Partners shifted their Citizen Science offerings to more online activities, fewer physical events and fewer outreach activities. The COVID-19- related activities on the platform, like the list of projects, were able to engage a growing audience.

In the 14 interviews that were conducted with partners from all parts of Europe we learned a lot about the differences between European countries and institutions, when it comes to the establishment, support and uptake of Citizen Science as a scientific approach. We find countries with established national platforms, information centres and even funding programs for Citizen Science, and on the other side of the spectrum countries where central support structures for Citizen Science are still in their infancy or not existing yet. However, awareness for Citizen Science is growing in all countries, but we learned that even in "frontrunner"-countries a large number of scientists are not aware of how to best use Citizen Science for their work. Another general challenge is the funding of activities that, if existent, needs to be renegotiated regularly.

Also the organisational commitment towards Citizen Science varies a lot across organisations in Europe. In some cases Citizen Science has been recognised as a strategic objective and is thus given structural support in the form of funding for Citizen Science activities or the establishment of Citizen Science labs. While in other partner organisations Citizen Science is still driven by the personal interest of individuals, without any specific organisational support.

The involvement in the EU-Citizen.Science project is for all partner organisations - no matter whether they have well established Citizen Science infrastructures or not - a means to increase reputation and visibility for their Citizen Science activities and an opportunity to leverage national endeavours. It is expected to support the communication activities for awareness raising on Citizen Science, to mainstream and increase interest as well as training. Being part

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of the EU-Citizen.Science project also means building up own competencies and getting new inputs and ideas, as partners are close to important information and a network of experts in Citizen Science.

All partners have already been involved in a large number of activities to promote Citizen Science, partly driven by individual involvement without any structural support at hand. In general the consortium provides access to all relevant stakeholder groups of Citizen Science, and addressing specific target groups for a wide and inclusive promotion of Citizen Science will be a focus of the final project year.

In their planning for 2021, partner organisations have already indicated a large set of activities addressing very different target groups. These range from dedicated meetings with policy representatives to trigger national Citizen Science strategies, to schools activities and large public events. Likewise we will see more national Citizen Science platforms emerge in the coming year.

Interviews that are organised at the time of writing this deliverable and again at the end of the project will follow up on these activities and the further establishment of Citizen Science in the different organisational contexts and countries.

And there are more observations on the European level: At the policy level we see Citizen Science being taken up widely in current and future funding programmes, such as the **Green Deal Call 10.3. Enabling citizens to act on climate change, for sustainable development and environmental protection through education, Citizen Science, observation initiatives, and civic engagement**¹⁹ where Citizen Science is specially addressed. Also the upcoming **Horizon Europe** funding programme should contribute to mainstreaming Citizen Science, suggesting it as a cross-cutting methodology in an overall mission oriented approach. Recommendations are also included in the report “Citizen Science and Citizen Engagement - Achievements in Horizon 2020 and recommendations on the way forward”²⁰.

DG Environment is recognising Citizen Science as an important instrument for environmental monitoring²¹ and recognizes “*the volume of environmental knowledge generated by Citizen Science initiatives across the EU*” as “*a unique opportunity to help deliver on the European Green Deal and other EU (and global) priorities, and to involve the public in EU policy-making*”. Many partner representatives of the project have contributed to this strategic recognition of Citizen Science for environmental monitoring.

National funding programmes are emerging in various countries in Europe, e.g. Spain, Portugal, Germany, Austria, UK and the Netherlands, to name a few. National Citizen Science platforms are also on the rise: the current working group of national platforms meets regularly to address challenges, like funding, organization of workloads and framing of

¹⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/lc-gd-10-3-2020>

²⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/research_and_innovation/research_by_area/documents/ec_rtd_swafs_report-citizen_science.pdf

²¹ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/legal/reporting/pdf/best_practices_citizen_science_environmental_monitoring.pdf

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Citizen Science, and is in close exchange with EU-Citizen.Science, not only technically via an API which allows the integration of project data from national platforms to the EU-Citizen.Science portal, but also bundles forces in addressing the above mentioned challenges. The conference “Knowledge for Change: A decade of Citizen Science (2020-2030) in support of the SDGs”²² that was organised during the German presidency received wide attention with around 500 registered visitors. In terms of knowledge and awareness, the ECSA Characteristics of Citizen Science²³ with 1,730 views on Zenodo and being the most downloaded resource on the platform, is an indication of the growing interest in the topic and that there is a need for a wider understanding of what Citizen Science is and how it can be practiced.

While it is clear that we cannot assign these developments exclusively to the work done in this project, there are indications that the activities of this consortium clearly contributed to the policy generation related to Citizen Science.

The final evaluation and impact assessment report (Deliverable D7.3) will again integrate all the different aspects mentioned above and draw conclusions towards the impact and long term outcomes the project has achieved.

²² <https://www.cs-sdg-conference.berlin/en/>

²³ <https://zenodo.org/record/3758668#.X8es-6pKhTY>